

Modelling Tool Evaluation Survey

Before starting with the sheet, please make user your have already read through the explanatory statement and agree to continue in the consent form.

Your responses are anonymous. While waiting for others to arrive, we would like to collect some background information about participants.

* Indicates required question

1. What is your pronouns? *

Mark only one oval.

- He/Him/His
- She/Her/Her
- They/Them/Their
- Prefer not to reply
- Other: _____

2. Are you a student or academic? *

Mark only one oval.

- PhD/Master student
- Academic
- Business/Industry
- Other: _____

3. Which categories best describe you? *

Tick all that apply.

- Software engineer
- System architect
- Business analyst/business manager
- Domain expert
- Other: _____

Project introduction & Initial diagram

Our researchers will first introduce you a case study of designing an eHealth application, and ask you to draw the initial diagram of your own eHealth app with one or several existing visual notations, like UML, BPMN, data flow, ER diagram, as well as their own ad-hoc notations.

4. Which notation(s) did you choose to use? *

Tick all that apply.

- UML
- BPMN
- Flow Chart
- ER Diagram
- Mind map
- I made up my own ad hoc notation
- Other: _____

5. What is your reason for your choice in previous question? *

Introduce the new modelling tool

Our researchers will introduce you a new modelling language for eHealth application. It contains two different versions of visual notations, you can choose your preferred one for further steps.

6. Choose your preferred visual notations. *

Mark only one oval.

- Icon notations
- Shape notations

7. What is your reason for your choice in previous question? *

8. What is the Page ID of your initial diagram? *

9. What is the User ID of your new diagram made by new visual notations? *

Exchange diagrams

Your will be asked to exchange your diagrams with others and compare the allocated diagrams.

10. What is the Page ID of your received initial diagram? *

11. What is the User ID of your received diagram made by new visual notations? *

12. Which notation would you like to use to communicate with stakeholders? *

Mark only one oval.

- Other participants' initial diagram
- Other participants' diagram made by new notations
- Either
- Neither

13. What is the reason for your answer to the previous question? *

Evaluation of the new tool

In this section, you will be asked to evaluate the new modelling visual notations based on your using experience.

14. Please rate the difficulty of learning this new tool. *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Easy Difficult

15. Please rate the difficulty of using this tool. *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Easy Difficult

16. Please rate the difficulty of understanding others' diagrams made by the tool. *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Easy Difficult

17. What is the level of software engineering knowledge to use the tool? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very comprehensive knowledge

18. What is the level of programming language knowledge to use the tool? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Very Very comprehensive knowledge

19. Will you recommend this tool to others in the future? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Maybe

20. Please share us with your overall feeling of using this new modelling tool or leave your comments.

End of this survey

Thanks for your participants!

The results of this survey will be used for further evaluation and optimization of this tool. Please let our researchers know at the end of this study if you are interested to get a copy of this tool.

21. Were there any issues with this user study or survey design that you think should be changed?

Mark only one oval.

All good

Other: _____

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